

Book Review

The Australian Class Action: A 30-Year Perspective by Michael Legg and James Metzger (eds)

Reviewed by Anton Burri*

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The Australian Class Action: A 30-Year Perspective, by Michael Legg and James Metzger (eds), The Federation Press, 2023, 336 pages. Hardback: ISBN 9781760024253. eBook: ISBN 9781760024260. AU\$ 180.

If you are looking for the most up-to-date and comprehensive book on past and current developments of the Australian class action regime, look no further. This collection of essays edited by Dr Michael Legg and Dr James Metzger, professor and senior lecturer at the University of New South Wales, respectively, is a treasure trove full of analysis of and commentary on the genesis, operation, and societal implications of the Australian class action. The authors represent a select group of the most accomplished academics, judges, and practitioners, many of whom have been playing a leading role in making the regime what it is today and what it will become in the future.

The Australian class action regime, set out in *Pt IVA of the Federal Court of Australia Act 1976 (Cth)*, commenced in March 1992. In their opening chapter, the editors introduce the statutory framework and recount the cornerstone decisions that have shaped the system since its inception. Early decisions clarified key aspects, such as the requirements that the claims brought in a class action be in respect of the “same, similar or related circumstances”¹ and “give rise to a substantial issue of law or fact.”² Just after the turn of the millennium, the opt-out regime faced – and survived – challenges to its constitutionality.³ Beyond these fundamental decisions, courts grappled with issues such as litigation funding, managing multiple class actions, settlement, and statutory estoppel. In addition, the authors discuss how *Pt IVA* has spurred the adoption of class action regimes at the state level and how class actions have played out in different types of cases, ranging from investor and shareholder class actions to public interest cases. An ideal primer for the uninitiated and a valuable guide to the must-know developments in Australian class actions for practitioners and academics alike.

In his essay, Michael Legg explores the way how class actions contribute to access to justice and, in particular, access to compensation. He first reviews illustrative cases in which the class action was successfully used to recover significant compensation where it would otherwise not have been possible. He then identifies several factors that impede perfect compensation: risk inherent in litigation and the need for compromise in settlement, fees for lawyers and funders, and the high costs associated with class action proceedings. A potential shortcut to simplifying proceedings and reducing costs would be

*Anton Burri: Attorney-at-Law, MLaw, BLaw, BA (University of Lucerne), PhD Candidate at the University of Lucerne and the Erasmus University Rotterdam, funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF).

¹ *Zhang v Minister for Immigration, Local Government and Ethnic Affairs* (1993) 45 FCR 384.

² *Wong v Silkfield Pty Ltd* (1999) 199 CLR 255; [1999] HCA 48.

³ *Femcare Ltd v Bright* (2000) 100 FCR 331; [2000] FCA 512; *Mobil Oil Australia Pty Ltd v Victoria* (2002) 211 CLR 1; [2002] HCA 27.

awarding aggregate damages more often. Legg considers the promise and perils of aggregate damages and concludes that under Australian law, unlike in United Kingdom competition law, the compensation principle as a matter of substantive law still heavily limits their wider use. He ends on an appeal to find options to reduce costs in class actions without the introduction of sweeping reforms that would change the type of “justice” that is being delivered. His chapter in this regard is an important reminder that, generally, it is wiser to treat the cause, not the symptom.

The Hon Justice Michael Lee and Emerson Hynard focus on the interplay between access to justice and finality. One of the key features that allow class actions to provide access to justice for large numbers of people is the opt-out mechanism. At the same time, this mechanism facilitates finality because class members who do not opt out are bound by the judgment regardless of the outcome. What appears simple on the level of principle turns out to be rather complex if one zooms in on the question of what, precisely, should be the scope of a judgment’s binding effect on (aspects of) individual claims that may or may not have been explicitly addressed in the class action. The authors look through the microscope and carefully analyze how the doctrines of cause of action estoppel, issue estoppel, *Anshun* estoppel, and the court’s discretion in preventing abuse of its processes delineate the scope of class action judgments. In addition, they discuss how procedural tools such as class closures and common fund orders require judges to find a balance between access to justice and finality in class actions. Overall, the essay provides a clear analysis and invaluable guide for anyone who is involved in litigating claims that may be affected by a class action.

Class actions usually result in settlements. For a class action settlement to be binding, the court must approve it. Historically, courts rarely provided extensive justifications for their approval decisions and, at the parties’ request, generously used suppression orders to keep the terms of settlement agreements secret. The Hon Justice Jayne Jagot, the Hon Justice Bernard Murphy, and Aaron Moss discuss the trend towards – and the need for – greater scrutiny and transparency of settlement approvals: the representative nature of class actions and conflicts of interests between those involved mean that courts should take their gate keeper role seriously and explain their reasoning in approving a particular settlement as “fair and reasonable.” The authors insist that suppression orders be made only where “necessary to prevent prejudice to the proper administration of justice,”⁴ and echo the High Court’s warning that “necessary” is a “strong word.”⁵ Rightly so. Ultimately, the transparency guaranteed by the principle of open justice is of vital importance for the credibility and the legitimacy of the system. As the authors put it, “Justice must both be done and be seen to be done.”

Andrew Higgins examines due process rights in class actions – rights of class members from which the court cannot deviate. He contrasts these with case management principles, in the application of which the court has discretion and must balance different interests. A due process right Higgins thinks is underappreciated is the right to adequate representation. To his mind, courts in Australian class actions should – like in the United States – formally select and appoint representative parties. In contrast, he contends that the right to opt out has been construed too liberally. Since one of the central objectives of class actions is to avoid conflicting decisions, parties who decide to opt out should not be allowed to relitigate on their own accord claims that are based on the common issues decided in the class action. Higgins’s views may no doubt be controversial, but he makes a convincing case for focusing more on the system-wide implications of rights granted to individuals in class actions.

Class actions are costly and risky. Therefore, one of the fundamental questions that arise before a class action is even filed is the question of financing. Peter Cashman shares his experiences with the funding of group litigation, mass torts, and class actions over the last 40 years in “the Trenches and the Ivory Tower” as law reformer, solicitor, barrister, and academic. He reports that the drafters of *Pt IVA* (among whom Cashman himself) were well aware of the centrality of an appropriate funding mechanism, but

⁴ *Federal Court of Australia Act 1976* (Cth) s 37AG(1)(a).

⁵ *Hogan v Australian Crime Commission* (2010) 240 CLR 651, 654 [30]; [2010] HCA 21.

the issue was ultimately not addressed in the legislation to reach a political compromise. In the early years, class actions were funded by lawyers via no-win no-fee agreements. But, as those turned out to be too heavily restricted and recommendations to introduce a public fund to support class actions were never followed, commercial third-party litigation funding soon became the dominant source of financing. Cashman not only gives a vivid account of these historic developments, but also provides an insider's perspective on many of the cases in which he was involved. The combination of institutional analysis with anecdotal as well as quantitative evidence makes this chapter mandatory reading for all with an interest in the financial side of class actions.

“Lawyers who work on class actions spend a lot of time in the moment,” notes Peta Spender. Her essay provides an opportunity to take a step back and look at the bigger picture. She deploys the framework of regulatory and institutional theory to approach the ultimate question: are class actions a good or a bad thing? In search for an answer, she explores the regulatory role of the class action, but also cautions against the risk of rent-seeking behavior by profit-oriented actors. Furthermore, Spender examines class action case law, pointing out that earlier decisions fall into the category of autonomous law, following closely the rules on the books. Later decisions adopt a more responsive approach, not just taking guidance from the statutory text but also taking into account the needs emerging from social dynamics. The decision in *Money Max Int Pty Ltd v QBE Insurance Group Ltd*, in which the Full Federal Court confirmed the court's power to make common fund orders, is singled out as venturing too far into the political process.⁶ In reaction, she argues, a shift of the debate away from judicial to political fora followed. An important lesson from Spender's contribution is that courts need to find a balance between ensuring that the class action system works as intended and, at the same time, respecting the boundaries set by legislation to not undermine their integrity.

Ben Chen and Michael Legg examine the Australian class action through the lens of economic theory. They discuss the costs and benefits associated with class actions and provide a useful framework for analyzing many of the central policy issues arising in class actions, such as cost sharing, conflicts of interests, free-riding problems, deterrence of wrongdoing, or the impact of transaction costs. The law-and-economics approach they adopt focuses on the incentives which the law shapes. This makes it ideally suited for evaluating existing and designing new institutional arrangements considering their likely consequences on the behavior of the involved actors. Chen and Legg illustrate the analytical power of the economic models by examining three potential regulatory regimes for litigation funding: reliance on market forces, court oversight, and a statutory percentage cap on funding fees. This essay will be particularly useful for those who are interested in policy issues and regulatory reforms relating to class actions.

James Metzger assesses the class action against the core values of a democratic society. As a first step, he traces the developments of modern democracy in the United States and Australia to distill some of the key principles that define a democratic society: those who are governed should, on the one hand, have a say in who governs them and, on the other hand, be in a position to hold those who govern them to account. As a second step, Metzger demonstrates that those who are affected by the conduct of the class action – the class members – have virtually no influence on who represents them – the representative party and their lawyers – and equally limited means to hold them accountable. Metzger calls upon the courts to ensure the protection of the affected claimholders' autonomy, lest the class actions device might work to undermine the principles on which our democracies rest.

Much of the academic discourse on class actions focuses on normative ideals such as access to justice, efficiency, and the protection of claimholders' rights. Amid these lofty aspirations, Linda S Mullenix reminds us that, in actuality, class action reform is highly politicized and that the current framework is the outcome of a constant power struggle between various interest groups. She puts into the spotlight

⁶ *Money Max Int Pty Ltd v QBE Insurance Group Ltd* (2016) 245 FCR 191, [176]; [2016] FCAFC 148.

the “political hydraulics” at play and explains how in the United States both the plaintiff and the defense bar – together with their allies – try to shape the law in their respective interests. She meticulously describes the various attempts by interest groups to influence the rule- and law-making processes through the Advisory Committee on Civil Rules, the American Law Institute, and the United States Congress. While Mullenix reassures us that the most extreme proposals of either side have failed to dramatically transform the system, it is worth keeping in mind the politicking likely going on behind the scenes of the academic discourse not just in the US, but also in current class action reforms in Australia and Europe.

In the concluding chapter, Rachel Mulheron discusses the case of *Paccar Inc v Road Haulage Association Ltd (Paccar)*,⁷ writing when the case was still pending before the Supreme Court of the United Kingdom. At issue in *Paccar* was whether litigation funding agreements qualify as so-called damages-based agreements (DBAs), to which certain strict rules apply. Mulheron convincingly argues that litigation funding agreements should not be treated as DBAs. The Competition Appeal Tribunal as well as the Court of Appeal agreed with her. However, on 26 July 2023, the Supreme Court sent shockwaves across the class action industry in the United Kingdom when it decided that agreements by which a litigation funder is entitled to remuneration based on the awarded damages do qualify as DBAs. Accordingly, such litigation funding agreements are unenforceable if they do not comply with DBA regulations (which they typically do not), and they cannot be used at all to fund opt-out collective proceedings before the Competition Appeal Tribunal. Mulheron’s discussion of the case illustrates the centrality of third-party funding for both the Australian and the UK class action regimes. It also shows how a single court decision – Mulheron points to *BMW Australia Ltd v Brewster*⁸ – can fundamentally change the viability of funding and, therefore, the availability of class actions. These cases are a reminder that, although the Australian and the UK class action regimes are set out in the law, they are not set in stone. They will continue to evolve. It will be interesting to see what the next decades will bring in this regard.

In his foreword to the anthology, the Hon Justice Michelle Gordon AC concludes: “All who have to participate in or think about the conduct of [class action] cases now and in the future (whether practitioner, scholar, student or the legislature) will benefit from this collection of essays.” To this, nothing needs to be added.

⁷ *Paccar Inc v Road Haulage Association Ltd* [2021] EWCA Civ 299; on 26 July 2023, the UK Supreme Court gave its judgment in *R (on the application of PACCAR Inc and others) (Appellants) v Competition Appeal Tribunal and others (Respondents)* [2023] UKSC 28.

⁸ *BMW Australia Ltd v Brewster* [2019] HCA 45; (2019) 94 ALJR 51.